

RESEARCH ARTICLE

Memory State Dynamics in BEOL FeFETs: Impact of Area Ratio on Analog Write Mechanisms and Charging

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ABSTRACT This work presents dynamic state writing by combining ferroelectric (FE) polarization together with charge injection (CI) on Si-based ferroelectric MOSFETs as a novel approach for non-volatile memory design. FE capacitors are non-destructively integrated in the Back-End-of-Line (BEOL) with Si MOSFETs to create FE-Metal-FETs (FeMFETs). We explore the FE/MOS area ratio (AR) as a critical design parameter, particularly in the context of dynamic writing processes, where various voltage pulse trains are applied for analog potentiation and depression of the memory state. AR significantly influences both the electric field distribution over the FE and the extent of CI from the top electrode. Constant-pulse writing schemes enable analog threshold voltage modulation by considering the AR, with reduced voltages and faster operation for smaller ARs. Retention of intermittent states written by FE polarization combined with CI is demonstrated, illustrating the stability and effectiveness of FeMFET devices and AR optimization for memory applications.

INDEX TERMS BEOL integration, CMOS, FeFET, ferroelectricity, HZO, non-volatile memory, switching dynamics.

I. INTRODUCTION

Ferroelectric $\text{Hf}_{0.5}\text{Zr}_{0.5}\text{O}_2$ (HZO) has been extensively studied as a promising material for non-volatile memory [1], [2]. This is due to the non-volatile polarization switching in FE thin-film HZO driven by an applied electric field. The polarization can then be used as a memory state, either as a measured control of polarization switching currents in FE Random-Access Memory (FERAM) or as electrostatic control of a band structure. This could be used in a so-called FE Tunnel Junction (FTJ) where the tunneling current is modulated, or in a FE MOSFET (FeFET) where the voltage threshold is shifted depending on the polarized state. FE HZO is also interesting due to its switching dynamic where analog control of the degree of polarization can be controlled

by voltage-pulse writing width (t_w) and amplitude (V_w), and tuned in different ways with, for instance, material composition [3], [4].

As a device capable of analog memory states and ultra-low power consumption, as well as being a three-terminal device separating the program and non-destructive read processes, FeFETs are a candidate for non-volatile and low-power memory devices, with applications in neuromorphic and in-memory computing [1], [5], [6], [7].

Due to the CMOS-compatibility of HZO integration, it has been a focus of many studies for Front-End-of-Line (FEOL) integration. While HZO-integration on ultra-scaled MOSFETs is attractive due to footprint, several challenges remain to be addressed for these devices. For instance, current path percolation, state retention and device endurance are issues arising from non-uniform FE domain switching, depolarization fields and charge trapping at the

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FIGURE 1. (a) False colored SEM micrograph (tilted) of BEOL electrodes (TE & BE: Top & Bottom Electrode) and the MFM capacitor (red). (b) Schematic of BEOL integration and MFM-MOS connection. (c) Simplified process flow, described more in detail in section II.

FE-semiconductor interface [8], [9], [10], [11], [12], [13]. Further, when the HZO is scaled to its discrete FE grains, analog control of the FeFET state decreases [14].

BEOL FE integration is a potential solution to these challenges. By connecting a metal-FE-metal (MFM) capacitor in series to the MOS gate metal in the form of a so-called FE-Metal-FET (FeMFET), the polarization charge from the FE HZO will be screened to avoid percolation and retention issues. Additionally, the design freedom of using optimized FEOL together with compatible BEOL processing may allow for highly specific system design. For instance, the operating voltage may be tailored as a function of the capacitive ratio between the MFM and MOS, resulting in lower operating voltages compared to normal FeFETs [15]. This flexibility and tuneability argue for the benefits of FeMFETs compared to FeFETs for applications where this is desired, despite a lesser focus on node scaling.

While FE HZO has received attention for its low-power, non-volatile, fast and analog operations, there are other technologies with potential for non-volatile memory devices. Resistive RAM (RRAM) is widely studied due to its simple two-terminal design, operation speed and scalability, but suffers from issues such as reliability due to variable filament formations [16]. Phase-change memories (PCM) are relatively mature and have displayed performance in system-scale implementations with analog states, however with challenges in power consumption and scaling due to high required currents [17]. Flash memories are industrially implemented and widely used but faces issues when it comes to in-memory computing due to challenges in programming speed, high write voltages, analog precision and endurance [5].

Here, we present a BEOL integration scheme of MFM capacitors in a 180-nm-node Si CMOS technology. Similar integration schemes have been presented and evaluated in previous studies [15], [18], [19], [20], [21], [22]. In [18], back-gated IWO-channel FeFETs are integrated in BEOL and show analog behavior from pulsed writing, however

without a separate MFM capacitor to the MOS structure. In [19], MFM-MOS area ratios (AR) on Si-channel FeMFETs are investigated in respect to biasing amplitude and time, however without investigation into analog states and pulse train writing. In [20], the AR of Si-based FeMFETs is optimized to maximize the memory window (MW) in digital memories as a balance between voltage drop over the FE film and I_{on}/I_{off} . In [21] and [22], semiconducting oxide (IGZO) FETs integrated with HZO-based MFM capacitors show that charge injection (CI) from the top electrode (TE) to the MFM-MOS middle electrode (identical to the MFM bottom electrode (BE)) takes place when the voltage drop over the MFM (V_{MFM}) is sufficiently large.

This CI adds charges of the same polarity as the TE bias to the BE and can widen the MW significantly [22], [23]. This effect is mainly demonstrated by I-V sweeps, and although a pulse train is used to achieve analog states, as a consequence the type of pulse train or its frequency is not investigated. Further, the retention of analog states is not presented. Regarding the effect of AR and charging on the analog pulsed writing dynamics, further studies are clearly needed.

In this work, the MFM-MOS AR is explored as a design parameter for BEOL FeMFETs, establishing in a new way its role in tunable analog memory state dynamics. While the effect of AR in FeMFETs has previously been investigated with a main focus on MW or static measurements, we take a new approach and extend these investigations into analog state writing utilizing varied electric pulse schemes that combines both FE polarization and CI. It is shown that analog states can be written in a controlled way with writing schemes varying both pulse train amplitude, width and repetitions. Due to a combination of FE state-change and CI from the FeMFET TE, the AR has a notable effect on required write pulse width and amplitude, in a way that can be applicable for tunable dynamic responses, where different dependencies between the pulse train and the memory state can be achieved. The degree of CI can be determined by AR as well as the pulse train amplitude and width, and a separation of FE and FE+CI states can be observed under various conditions. The AR is also varied to show that different degrees of multi-level operation is achievable. We demonstrate for the first time retention measurements of states written with varying pulse widths as a method of illustrating the feasibility of FE-and FE+CI-written states.

These findings address a knowledge gap in the study of FeMFET analog dynamics, illustrating the potential for tailored device designs in neuromorphic and in-memory computing.

II. EXPERIMENTAL

The BEOL integration of HZO was performed on a commercial 180 nm node CMOS package provided by XFAB (XH018), and is illustrated in Fig. 1 (a-b). The underlying MOSFETs were designed with MOS areas ranging from 10 to 50 μm^2 , keeping a W/L ratio of 0.3 for identical current densities. A simplified process flow is shown

in Fig. 1 (c). The shipped wafers were processed up to top metal 3 (Al), with a $1.8 \mu\text{m}$ thick $\text{Si}_3\text{N}_4/\text{SiO}_2$ top spacer and planarized with a consequent chemical mechanical polishing (CMP) step. FEOL CMOS device access was achieved by via etching through the top spacer, using a CHF_3 -based dry-etch plasma that would stop at the Al top metal with an etch ratio that was determined to be $>100x$. Prior to the via opening etch, an etch stop layer consisting of a 30 nm-thick Al_2O_3 was deposited by atomic layer deposition (ALD), which was also removed in the areas of the vias prior to via opening using an Al-wet-etch procedure. Via metallization was performed with sputtering of 100 nm of TiW, where in-situ Ar-bombardment was used to remove the native oxide of the top metal prior the metallization. The localization of the TiW was performed with a CF_4 -based dry-etch plasma, where the etch ratio to the Al_2O_3 stopping layer was determined to be about 10x. A second metallization was then performed to deposit the BE, where 30 nm TiN was sputtered. The TiN film had prior been optimized for strong $\langle 111 \rangle$ orientation, low surface roughness (0.92 nm RMS), and relatively high film stress (580 MPa). The TiN film was etched into finger-like electrodes (Fig. 1 (a)) using a CF_4 -based plasma, where the etch ratio to the Al_2O_3 -layer was determined to be $>10x$.

Vias to the MOSFET gate and probing pads were separately contactable. A 10 nm HZO layer was grown on top of the TiN BE by ALD at 200°C with alternating cycles of TDMA(Hf/Zr) precursors and water as oxygen source (similar to the process in [24]). A TE of W was sputtered and then patterned by lithography and dry-etching based on SF_6 to define a HZO etch mask. The exposed HZO (not to be used as the MFM capacitor) was wet-etched with buffered HF, followed by additional W sputtering (for a total W thickness of 80 nm) to connect the TE with the vias leading to the gate probing pads. Subsequently, annealing of the device was performed at 450°C for 30 s in N_2 environment. The TE was again patterned by dry-etching based on SF_6 to define the finger structure and the MFM area, illustrated in Fig. 1 (a-b).

The exact MFM area (and thus the AR) was determined by scanning electron microscopy (SEM) (Fig. 1 (a)). Finally, probing pad metal was deposited (5 nm Ti + 200 nm Au) and patterned with a lift-off process.

Electrical characterization was performed in an MPI probe station at room temperature in a shielded chamber, using a Keysight B1500 Semiconductor Analyzer and B1530a Waveform Generators, SMUs and E5288A AttoSense units for pulse biasing and high-resolution I-V measurements. All measurements for a certain AR were performed on the same device. The measurement sequencing and timing was kept identical for all comparative measurements.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

FE polarization of the HZO thin-film was verified after integration in Fig. 2 (a). The cycled hysteresis show a saturated polarization for the switching bias (3.5 MV/cm, corresponding to 3.5 V). Additionally, I-V transfer

FIGURE 2. (a) Polarization hysteresis of a $4 \mu\text{m}^2$ MFM capacitor (pristine and cycled (3.5 V, 1000 cycles, 1 kHz)). (b) I-V transfer of identical NMOS devices before and after processing. (c) Calculated V_{MFM}/V_{TOT} as a function of MFM and MOS area (according to eq. (1), with investigated ARs marked).

characteristics of reference CMOS transistors showed no detrimental effects from processing (Fig. 2 (b)).

The MFM-MOS capacitive ratio (CR) is determined by the AR, and the resulting MFM voltage drop is calculated as

$$V_{MFM} = \frac{V_{TOT}}{1 + C_{MFM}/C_{MOS}}, \frac{C_{MFM}}{C_{MOS}} \propto AR = \frac{A_{MFM}}{A_{MOS}}, \quad (1)$$

where V_{TOT} is the applied total voltage and $AR = A_{MFM}/A_{MOS}$, illustrated in Fig. 2 (c) with the investigated ARs (1/6, 1/11, 1/16 and 1/33) marked. As the choice of AR is important for MW considerations because of this voltage division, the selected ARs should cover a wide range of V_{MFM}/V_{TOT} ratios [20], [22], [23].

The AR scales approximately with a factor of 2 between the two largest (1/6 and 1/11) and the two smallest (1/16 and 1/33) values respectively. The dimensions were selected for convenient processing in the BEOL technology. The capacitance density C_{MFM} and C_{MOS} used for the calculations in eq. (1) are $20 \text{ fF}/\mu\text{m}^2$ and $5.3 \text{ fF}/\mu\text{m}^2$, respectively.

To study the analog state update of FeMFET devices with different ARs, a voltage-modulated pulse train for both programming and erasing states (potentiation (POT) and depression (DEP), respectively) was applied, with different t_w tested individually (Fig. 3 (a)). Between each POT-DEP step I-V transfer was measured to study the current evolution (Fig. 3 (b), (c), (d), (e) for AR=1/6, 1/11, 1/16 and 1/33 respectively).

All ARs show a clear POT-DEP succession. For $t_w=1 \mu\text{s}$ (i, ii in Fig. 3), the POT and DEP result in relatively similar MW (width of the shift in threshold voltage) for all ARs. Here, it is important to consider that the slope of the I-V is also

FIGURE 3. (a) Potentiation-Depression (POT-DEP) pulse train, by increasing write pulse amplitude (± 0.5 to ± 6 V, ± 0.25 V steps). (b-e) I-V transfer characteristics for AR: 1/6 (b), 1/11 (c), 1/16 (d) and 1/33 (e), for each POT step (i, iii) and DEP step (ii, iv) with $t_W: 1 \mu s$ (i, ii) and 10 ms (iii, iv). I_D measured with $V_D=100$ mV. The ring-marked line indicates a write pulse amplitude of ± 4 V.

affected by the AR as less voltage over the MOS is present for smaller ARs. This causes the I-V slopes to degrade (as well as the inherent V_T to increase) for smaller ARs, as is observed in Fig. 3 (b-e).

For AR=1/6, $V_W=\pm 4$ V (indicated by the ring-marked line) show that the MW still continues to grow above ± 4 V, which indicates that V_{MFM} has not reached high enough magnitude for complete FE switching (Fig. 2 (a)). For all other ARs (at $t_W=1 \mu s$), the MW is saturated around $V_W=\pm 4$ V as V_{MFM} is closer to the total applied voltage $V_{TOT}=V_W$ (eq. (1)) and reaches a saturated polarization switching around ± 4 V.

When increasing t_W to 10 ms (iii, iv in Fig. 3), AR=1/6 show no significant MW widening while all other smaller ARs show a distinct MW widening, increasing as the AR is decreasing. This widened MW is due to CI from the TE to the BE through the HZO, resulting from a sufficiently large V_{MFM} and long t_W [21], [22].

CI into the BE can occur from either the MOSFET channel or the TE. The AR would determine the voltage ratio of the MFM and the MOS, thus determining the dominant

process, as shown in [21], [22], and [23]. Here, the AR allows for a V_{MFM} large enough so a positive bias on the TE attracts negative charges from the BE through the MFM insulator, effectively inserting positive charges to the BE (directly in contact with the MOSFET gate metal), adding an additional biasing to the MOSFET in the same direction as FE polarization after a positive write. This applies for negative TE biasing as well. The effect of the CI adds up with the FE polarization to set the state of the FeMFET, since both the FE process and the TE-to-BE CI process would decrease V_T from positive biasing (POT) and increase V_T from negative biasing (DEP) [22]. This is in contrast to CI dominating from the MOS channel. Such CI between the MOS to the HZO interface is detrimental to memory operations in FeFETs, as it screens the FE polarization charge and cancels the FE effect (effectively closing the MW) [6].

For the larger AR (1/6), t_W have less effect on the MW, since a large enough field over the MFM for CI is not reached in any case. The CI is thus separated from the purely FE contribution for AR=1/6 for all t_W and for AR 1/11, 1/16, 1/33 for a short enough t_W ($1 \mu s$).

FIGURE 4. I_D versus POT-DEP (blue-red) pulse number with different t_W , for AR: 1/6 (a), 1/11 (b), 1/16 (c) and 1/33 (d). The write pulse amplitude in the sequence (from Fig. 3 (a)) is shown in the bottom x-axis. The voltage values for V_{MFM} according to eq. (1) differs for each AR and is shown in the top x-axis. I_D read at $V_G=0.5$ V, $V_D=100$ mV.

CI is both a field and time-driven process, and using the write pulse train accordingly is important for either separating CI from FE polarization in the memory state mechanism, or for tuning it to a desired degree. Interestingly, the DEP operation following the POT for AR=1/33 at $t_W=10$ ms shows very little modulation in Fig. 3 (e) for pulses below -4 V. The large field over the MFM at this timescale injects enough positive charges during POT to make negative writing difficult until a certain threshold. This is not seen at shorter time scales where this CI is limited, or for a larger AR where the field over the MFM is not as large. A large positive CI into the internal metal node thus seems detrimental for the DEP dynamic operation.

The analog writing dynamics of the FeMFETs are mapped in Fig. 4 (a-d), demonstrated by I_D at a certain read voltage ($V_G=0.5$ V) and as a function of V_W in the voltage-modulated pulse train (as seen in Fig. 3 (a)). The POT-DEP process is performed for various t_W . The different current ranges (I_{MIN} to I_{MAX}) in Fig. 4 are due to V_{MOS}/V_{TOT} being reduced as the AR decreases, resulting in different current levels for different devices at identical biasing (as seen in Fig. 3).

A saturation of the current level versus V_W is seen when I_D stops increasing even when V_W continues to increase. This happens for lower and lower V_W as AR is decreased, but for similar V_{MFM} (extracted in Fig. 4 for the different ARs). The saturation of the current modulation is, as discussed above, due to the complete FE polarization switching, and happens for either large enough AR or short enough t_W . The saturation is hidden in the contribution of

FIGURE 5. (a) POT-DEP pulse train, by identical repeating pulses at a certain V_W . (b) I-V transfer characteristics for AR: 1/11, for each POT step (i, iii) and DEP step (ii, iv), with $t_W=1 \mu\text{s}$ (i, ii) and $t_W=10$ ms (iii, iv), at $V_W=\pm 5$ V. An I-V readout before the first pulse is drawn as a black line. $V_D=100$ mV.

CI on the memory state (I_D shift) when the AR is small enough and t_W long enough. For A=1/33 (Fig. 4 (d)), the t_W dependence due to CI reaches a point at $t_W=10$ ms where the negative state dynamics is shifted further along the DEP pulse train, illustrating the detrimental effect of CI on the DEP operation seen in Fig. 3 (e, iv). This needs to be considered for controllable POT-DEP writing schemes.

While the writing dynamics in Fig. 4 is not necessarily linear in all cases, both the AR and the pulse train can be tuned for either maximum linearity or to tailor the dynamics for the device to benefit specific application, such as in neuromorphic computing. It has been shown that treating the plasticity dynamics of a synaptic weight as a tuneable parameter is beneficial for the performance of biologically inspired spiking neural networks, and a way to realize systems that evolve in their learning capabilities over time [25], [26], [27]. This could potentially be realized as a modulation of t_W in Fig. 3 (a) for a transition between a saturating and an exponential weight update, or from using multiple AR devices with various routing schemes.

By applying a pulse train of identical pulses, the POT-DEP behaviour could be modulated by only varying the number of pulses. Typically state change in HZO-based memristors shows non-linear POT-DEP from such pulse train [28]. In Fig. 5, the POT of FeMFETs from identical pulses is studied. Fig. 5 (a) illustrates this pulse train, where both t_W and V_W are kept constant throughout the specific measurements. The I-V transfer for an AR=1/11 FeMFET and $V_W=\pm 5$ V is shown in Fig. 5 (b), where an increase in t_W shows the effect of added CI for both POT (i, iii) and DEP (ii, iv) behaviour. Again, a smaller t_W (i-ii: $1 \mu\text{s}$) allows for less CI, while longer t_W (iii-iv: 10 ms) show a gradual state update.

FIGURE 6. (a-b) Voltage (read at $I_D=10^{-5} \mu A/\mu m$), versus POT pulse number (from Fig. 5 (a)) for AR: 1/11 (a) and 1/33 (b). V_W and t_W were varied between different POT processes, as +3, +4, +5 V and 10 ms to 1 μ s respectively. $V_D=100$ mV.

While DEP also operate more analog for longer t_W , the effect is larger for POT. By anchoring the current at $10^{-5} \mu A/\mu m$, the corresponding voltage is used to study the effective voltage-based POT state shift in Fig. 6 (a-b) for AR=1/11 (a) and 1/33 (b). Pulse 0 corresponds to an initial measurement after the SET operation. Here, smaller AR values show tunable voltage state modulation in cases where larger AR values do not, as an effect of incorporated CI together with FE polarization in writing a memory state. AR=1/33 enables similar tunable voltage states in the FeMFET as for AR=1/11 with either a lower required V_W or shorter t_W , seen in Fig. 6 (a-b) where the response from AR=1/33 roughly matches that for AR=1/11 for identical t_W and 1 V lower V_W , or for identical V_W and approximately one order of magnitude shorter t_W . This motivates scaled AR for reducing voltage and increasing speed for analog writing operations.

In an in-memory computing implementation, a constant-pulse scheme as described in Fig. 5 (a) would often be desired, for instance due to simplicity in the system [29]. Additionally, this type of pulse train is similar to action potentials pulses in biological neurons (constant width and amplitude), which could be beneficial in a neuromorphic system mimicking the operations of synapses and neurons as a spiking neural network [30]. A challenge with the constant-pulse scheme is that, if the circuitry responsible for the write pulse train is not flexible in terms of tuning amplitudes and pulse widths, the functionality relies heavily on the device dynamics. For this reason, it is important to investigate devices where the dynamic properties can be tunable to the desired effect.

The thickness d_{HZO} of the HZO in the MFM capacitor directly determines the electric field E_{MFM} induced by a

FIGURE 7. (a) Retention measurement scheme, where the state was written with successively longer t_W . Each individual state was read regularly up to 1000 s. (b-c) Retention measurements (room temperature) for AR: 1/11 (b) and 1/33 (c), done for states written with varying t_W (10 ms to 1 μ s). Retention measured as I_D sampled at $V_G=0.8$ V ($V_D=100$ mV). Dashed lines are a guide-to-the-eye extrapolation (linear, fitted to the last 4 measured data points for each t_W).

certain V_{MFM} (as $E_{MFM}=V_{MFM}/d_{HZO}$). This could be used to achieve FE switching at lower V_{MFM} , as the switching process is field-dependent. By decreasing d_{HZO} and keeping the same AR, the capacitive voltage division would be altered due to the increase in C_{MFM} , resulting in a lower V_{MFM} (according to eq. (1)). However, E_{MFM} would still always increase as a result of the reduced HZO thickness, regardless of AR. As an example, scaling $d_{HZO}=10$ nm (used in this study) to 5 nm at AR=1/11 decreases $V_{MFM} \approx 20\%$ but increases $E_{MFM} \approx 60\%$. This would be expected to lead to FE switching at lower applied voltages, as well as larger degrees of CI through the MFM. To note is that smaller HZO thicknesses generally lead to a higher required annealing temperature for desired FE crystallinity, which would be a limitation in BEOL-integration [1].

The state retention is evaluated at room temperature with a pulse scheme illustrated in Fig. 7 (a), measured after POT and DEP pulses with increasingly long t_W . The retention of FeMFETs with AR=1/11 and 1/33 is shown in Fig. 7 (b)

and (c) respectively. $AR=1/33$ shows a larger variation in I_D states (mainly for POT) with t_W , which is expected due to the larger dependence on t_W for CI. The DEP process shows increasing current levels for longer t_W , as the POT process becomes more and more detrimental to DEP with increasing t_W . Nonetheless, the current read-out shows good retention characteristics up to measurement end (1000 s), for both ARs and all t_W . While the actual current level magnitudes strongly depend on the choice of sampling V_G , the results illustrate stable memory states for all t_W , motivating AR-scalable FeMFETs for non-volatile memory devices with states written by both FE and FE+CI.

A smaller AR would yield a larger V_{MFM} as well as access to more CI. While sub- μm^2 MFM area scaling have been demonstrated [31], [32], there are also challenges to AR downscaling in the context of FeMFETs. A too small AR results in a very small V_{MOS} , degrading the transfer characteristics. Additionally, HZO directly integrated in the gate stack of ultrascaled FeFETs show discrete domain switching [14]. FE grain sizes of approximately 10 nm quantifies the number of purely FE states, which for ultra-scaled MFM capacitors could be detrimental for analog operations where CI is not accessed (for example by using small enough t_W) [33].

Depending on the application and desired analog writing dynamics, AR should be designed for the intended pulse train. When there are strong demands on specific writing dynamics, the AR is a very flexible integration parameter that gives more freedom in the applied pulse train. Future studies will include reliability such as device-to-device variations, retention at elevated temperatures and endurance, as well as the use of the presented FeMFETs in a practical in-memory-computing macro.

IV. CONCLUSION

Different pulse trains were used to evaluate the effect of write pulse amplitude and width on potentiation and depression for Si-based BEOL-integrated FeMFETs. BEOL offers flexibility in system design where the MFM-MOS AR can be used as a design parameter to achieve the desired writing dynamics. A smaller AR allows accessing CI as an additional memory mechanism combined with the FE contribution, where the design of the pulse train can be used for tunable analog dynamics. FE+CI-enabled states are shown to be stable over time, further verifying the use of this programming mechanism.

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